

Developing *eui*-cytoplasmic male sterile lines and applying them in hybrid rice breeding

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In hybrid rice development, a serious problem associated with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines is poor panicle exertion, which reduces outcrossing rate and hybrid seed production. Gibberellic acid (GA₃) has been routinely used to solve this problem. Other problems arise from application of GA₃, however, including increased costs, reduced seed quality, and possible environmental hazards. Rugter and Carnahan (1981) reported a recessive mutant that can cause elongation of the uppermost internode, referred to as the *eui-1* gene. Since *eui* can play the same role as GA₃ when transferred into CMS lines, this finding has attracted much interest in the development of CMS lines. We generated *eui* mutants through irradiation on both maintainer (B) and restorer (R) lines and transferred *eui-1* into CMS lines in China to improve hybrid rice seed production efficiency (Yang 1998). We report here the discovery of a new *eui* gene, referred to as *eui-2*(t), and the development of several B and R lines with the *eui* gene (designated as eA and eR), as well as the development of several hybrids with *eui* CMS lines.

Table 1 shows the characteristics of four commercially released eA lines compared with their corresponding non-*eui*

isogenic A lines. Results indicated that both *eui-1* and *eui-2* significantly affected several height-related traits (plant height, panicle length, and panicle neck exertion) without affecting pollen sterility. In general, *eui-1* had a greater effect on these traits than *eui-2*. The expression of both genes appeared to be affected by genetic backgrounds. For example, *eui-1* had more spikelets panicle⁻¹ and higher exposed stigma percentage when transferred into a II-32 genetic background than in XA or G46.

Table 2 shows the yield performance and yield-related traits of the seven

hybrids developed from the *eui*-CMS lines compared with counterparts from their corresponding non-*eui* CMS lines from a complete randomized block design in the early season of 1999. In the XA background, *eui*-hybrids were ~10 cm taller than the non-*eui* hybrids; no difference was detected for the other traits. Thus, *eui-1* appeared to be completely dominant. In GA and II-32 genetic backgrounds, however, *eui* hybrids were only 4 cm taller than non-*eui* hybrids, and both were basically identical for all traits, except that the *eui* hybrid had significantly higher yield than the non-*eui* hybrid in the II-32 back-

Table 1. Comparison of seven agronomic traits between eA lines and their corresponding A lines.

CMS line	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle neck exertion (cm)	Spikelet panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet length (cm)	Stigma exertion (%)	Pollen abortive rate (%)
XeA ^a	91.53 a	23.25 a	1.62 a	107.8 a	0.94 a	—	—
XeA ^b	79.09 b	21.93 a	-4.55 b	126.1 a	0.95 a	29.5 a	94.1 a
XA (ck)	69.05 c	18.70 b	-7.10 c	106.8 a	0.90 a	25.6 a	91.0 a
II-32eA ^a	111.20 a	28.50 a	3.70 a	271.0 a	0.79 a	74.1 a	91.7 a
II-32A(ck)	86.00 b	25.30 b	-11.20 b	218.0 b	0.76 b	57.5 b	90.8 a
G46eA ^a	108.60 a	23.00 a	-9.73 a	241.2 a	0.74 a	24.5 a	99.5 a
G46A(ck)	91.05 b	22.65 a	-14.54 b	245.7 a	0.72 b	23.3 a	99.9 a

^aeA lines with (*eui-1 eui-1*) gene type, ^bLines with (*eui-2 eui-2*) gene type. Different letters indicate significant difference between eA and A lines at the 5% level.

Table 2. Comparison of yield and agronomic traits between some characters *eui* hybrids and non-*eui* hybrids.

Hybrid	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Total grain number	Seed set rate (%)	Effective panicles (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (g m ⁻²)
XA/R-127	123	101.0 b	25.8 a	106.9 a	89.9	9.1	31.8	561.7 a
XeA/eR-127 ^a	120	109.4 a	26.3 a	105.5 a	93.8	9.3	32.3	626.1 a
XeA ^b /eR-127 ^a	119	110.5 a	26.1 a	100.7 a	92.8	9.6	32.9	593.9 a
GA/R-127	125	117.1 b	27.9 a	141.6 a	91.1	9.3	29.4	533.4 a
GA/eR-127 ^a	123	121.8 a	28.0 a	145.0 a	92.7	9.2	29.5	544.7 a
II-32A/R-127	126	104.8 b	26.2 a	144.6 a	85.7	8.1	27.6	440.6 b
II-32eA ^a /R-127	124	108.3 a	27.4 a	145.4 a	85.7	8.1	28.6	531.7 a

^aeA lines with (*eui-1 eui-1*) gene type, ^bLines with (*eui-2 eui-2*) gene type. Different letters indicate significant difference between eA and A lines at the 5% level.

ground. This yield advantage was observed in many other *eui* hybrids (data not shown). Of these *eui*-hybrids, G46A/eR-127 is being tested in the Fujian provincial multilocation yield trials.

References

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Prediction of hybrid performance in rice: comparisons among best linear unbiased prediction (BLUP) procedure, midparent value, and molecular marker distance

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Since its success in China in the 1970s, hybrid rice technology has spread to other tropical countries such as India, Vietnam, Bangladesh, and the Philippines. Compared with inbred cultivars, the development of hybrid rice is more costly because it entails identification of parental lines that produce hybrids with superior yield. To reduce the number of crosses and the time consumed in field evaluation, an efficient prediction method for hybrid performance would be useful.

Midparent value (MPV), which is the average of both parents of a hybrid, is a classical method of predicting hybrid performance. This method, however, proved to be less efficient in predicting for traits with low heritability. Genetic distances derived from molecular markers were reported to have a certain significant correlation with hybrid yield performance, but this method is expensive. Notably, the best linear unbiased prediction (BLUP) procedure has been successfully applied to predict single-cross performance of maize and soybean (Bernardo 1994, Panter and Allen 1995).

The BLUP method, which combines field testing of related hybrids and acquiring pedigree information or molecular data, holds great promise in hybrid performance prediction (Charcosset et al 1998). This study compared the efficiency of the BLUP procedure, MPV, and marker distance derived from microsatellite DNA

assays in predicting F_1 hybrid performance in rice.

Rice lines used in this study were 66 F_1 hybrids derived from 10 cytoplasmic male sterile-wild abortive (CMS-WA) lines and 23 promising restorer lines. Field experiments were conducted at the UPLB farm in the 1998 dry season. Data were collected for 100-grain weight, single-plant yield, and panicle weight. DNA was extracted and purified following a modified CTAB procedure. The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) protocol and silver staining procedures were those used in the genetic laboratory of PhilRice. Thirty-seven primer pairs were used in the assay.

The MPV of a cross was defined as the mean of two parental lines. The pedigrees of parental lines of hybrid rice were traced back to ancestors that had no known pedigree information. Coefficient of parentage was estimated using the recursive method. The Nei and Li coefficient was used as a measure of genetic similarity.

The mixed linear model was assumed as $Y = X\beta + Za + Zd + e$, where Y is a vector of the observed hybrid yield, X and Z are known matrices, a is a vector of additive genetic effect, d is a vector of dominant genetic effects, and e is the vector of residual effects.

Correlation analyses were performed for MPV and the Nei and Li coefficient vs observed values. A set of 43 hy-

brids was used for generating additive, dominant, and residual variances, following the nest design (North Carolina design I) using SAS PROC GLM. BLUP-predicted values for the remaining 23 hybrids were obtained using a software developed by the senior author.

Results suggested a large dominant variance for plant yield. The highest heritability was noted for 100-grain weight, while single-plant yield and panicle weight had low to intermediate heritability (see table). With the BLUP procedure, predicted grain yield plant^{-1} and panicle weight were significantly correlated with observed values of F_1 hybrids. A highly significant linear relationship was found only between MPV and observations for 100-grain weight. There was no linear relationship between Nei-Li distance and any traits of F_1 hybrids (Figs. 1–3). Thus, the BLUP may be superior to MPV in predicting F_1 hybrid performance for low to intermediate heritable traits. The level of correlation can be improved if more accurate pedigree records and genetic variance estimates are acquired.

The BLUP procedure to be used in hybrid rice breeding programs has the following advantages:

- Only data of actual performance from related hybrids were required; field testing of parental lines was thus avoided.